

Saint Mary's University
School of Teacher Education and Humanities
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

I. **Title:** Pre-service Educators' Pandemic Experiences and Self-Care Activities

II. **Abstract:** Physical and mental health is a serious concern in a situation like pandemic. This is especially true to children and adolescents who are considered a vulnerable group. As the impact of COVID-19 continue to evolve, expressions of moods and anxiety problems will change. At an individual level, children and youth have suddenly lost many of the activities such as school, extracurricular activities, social interactions, and physical activity. These activities provide organization and sense of everyday life. As this crisis continues, these losses in the children's and youth's activities have had major impact on the youth's wellbeing. The study concludes that the mental health status of the pre-service educators is greatly challenged because of the current pandemic crisis. Majority of the students encounter problems related to personal, educational, and family concerns but they have developed self-care activities to maintain their physical and mental wellbeing. The study recommends that care support system such as the family and school extend assistance in the different aspects of life of the pre-service educators to help them become resilient and overcome the challenges brought about by the pandemic crisis. Specific strategies be crafted to address the problems encountered by the pre-service educators in relation to the personal, educational, and family concerns of the students. Modules on self-care activities be crafted and integrated in the CFE classes to uphold the students' holistic wellbeing.

Keywords: *pandemic experiences, pre-service educators, self-care activities*

III. **Project Description:** This study aimed to surface the experience of pre-service educators amidst the global pandemic and the activities they do to take care of themselves. The study was a qualitative research involving written interview with the pre-service educators. The findings of the study were used as basis in recommending the integration of the self-care lessons in the CFE classes.

IV. **Research Agenda:** Health and Wellness

V. **Name of Proponents:** Susan A. Galamay, PhD, Reiner Dulawan, MA, Marlon Saludaes, MA

VI. **Mechanism Applied For:** D (Collaborative Faculty Research Load)

VII. **Rationale**

The adolescent stage has been characterized with manifestations of high risk behavior, experimentation and early adaptation of adulthood characteristics. This scenario leads adolescents to encounter problems in adjusting to themselves and with society. These include behavioral problems, delinquency, lack of interest in studies, suicidal orientation, adolescence pregnancy, high risk sexual behavior and substance abuse (Azeez, 2015). As indicated in the previous study conducted on the students' level of mental health, findings showed that majority of the respondents had elevated values on a general screening test for mental health on Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), Oppositional Defiant Disorder (ODD), Conduct Disorder (CD), Separation Anxiety, General Anxiety, and Mood Disorder relative to normed values for 6-18 years old. This indicates that the students are predisposed or inclined to these mental conditions (Cachola et al., 2018).

Initial reports on the negative psychosocial correlates of the current COVID-19 pandemic are largely in line with these findings and increased depression, anxiety, and loneliness have been reported. Although safety measures are beginning to be lifted in many countries, health related outcomes may worsen due to economic uncertainties secondary to the COVID-19 pandemic.

As the impact of covid 19 continue to evolve, expressions of moods and anxiety problems will change. At an individual level, children and youth have suddenly lost many of the activities such as school, extracurricular activities, social interactions, and physical activity. These activities provide organization and sense of everyday life. As this crisis continues, these losses in the children's and youth's activities may aggravate depressive symptoms.

Mental health is a serious concern in a situation like pandemic. Children and adolescents are considered a vulnerable subgroup and there is a need to reduce the mental health burden of this pandemic (de Miranda, da Silva Athanasio, de Sena Oliveira, and Silva, 2020). This is corroborated in the study by Dvorsky, Breaux, and Becker (2020) which indicated that the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic presents tremendous challenges to child and adolescent health. It is expected that the COVID-19 crisis, including the disease and prolonged social distancing, will have a major impact on youth well-being.

The closures of the educational institution due to the outbreak of COVID-19 to control the spread of infection led to an unprecedented impact on education. During the lockdown, classes are now held online and teachers are instructed to teach through online learning platforms. As such, there is a need to implement innovative teaching for continuing education and to overcome mental stress and anxieties during the lockdown. The outbreak of COVID-19 results in the digital revolution. Higher education institutions are now conducting classes through online lectures, teleconferencing, digital open books, online examination, and interaction at virtual environments (Strielkowski, 2020). Online learning strategies are adopted to address the learning needs of students. However, the online mode of the teaching-learning process have posed challenges to students especially to the poor and marginalized ones (Manzoor, 2020). During this lockdown period, it imperative that the teaching-learning process be understood in the light of the pandemic situation in order to design effective interventions for meaningful teaching and learning (India Today, 2020).

It is in these contexts that this study, which aimed to surface the mental health status of the pre-service educators and determine the challenges they have encountered amidst this pandemic scenario as well as identify their self-care activities, was conceptualized.

Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to surface the pandemic experiences and self-care activities of the pre-service educators.

Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. determine the pre-service educators' pandemic experiences in terms of:
 - a. perceived mental health status
 - b. problems they have encountered
2. identify the pre-service educators' self-care activities

VIII. Theoretical framework of the Study

For physical and mental health promotion, self-care skills education is based on the teaching of generic life skills and includes the practice of skills in relation to major health and social problems, especially during challenging times like the present pandemic crisis. Self-care skills should be combined with health information, and may also be combined with other approaches, such as programmes designed to effect changes in environmental and social factors which influence the health and development of young people.

The methods used in the teaching of self-care skills builds upon what is known of how young people learn from their own experiences and from the people around them, from observing how others behave and what consequences arise from behaviour. This is described in the Social Learning Theory developed by Bandura (1977). In Social Learning Theory, learning is considered to be an active acquisition, processing and structuring of experiences. In self-care activities as part of life skills education, the youth are actively involved in a dynamic teaching and learning process. The methods used to facilitate this active involvement include working in small groups and pairs, brainstorming, role play, games and debates. A life skills lesson may start with a teacher exploring with the students what their ideas or knowledge are about a particular situation in which a life skill can be used. The children may be asked to discuss the issues raised in more detail in small groups or with a partner. They may then engage in short role play scenarios, or take part in activities that allow them to practice the skills in different situations - actual practice of skills is a vital component of life skills education. Finally, the teacher will assign homework to encourage the children to further discuss and practice the skills with their families and friends. Life skills have already been taught in many schools around the world. Some initiatives are in use in just a few schools, whilst in other countries, life skills programmes have been introduced in a large proportion of schools, and for different age groups.

Conceptual Framework

Inasmuch as it is the duty of educational institutions to uphold the wellbeing of its students specifically during this pandemic crisis, this study aimed to surface the pandemic experiences of the pre-service educators in terms of their present emotional status. This study also presented the problems encountered by the pre-service educators amidst the pandemic crisis.

The study also determined the self-care activities the pre-service educators were doing to attain wellbeing.

The findings of the study served as bases for integrating self-care lessons in the CFE classes.

X. Scope and Delimitation

This study aimed to surface the pre-service educators' pandemic experiences and self-care activities. The study was conducted among pre-service educators who were chosen through purposive sampling during the first semester of the SY 2020-2021. Data were gathered through written interview guide questions lifted from the webinar series of the World Health Organization (WHO) Office of the Secretary-General's Envoy on Youth. The guide questions of the written interview were limited to the questions raised in the webinar series. The findings of the study were used as basis for the crafting of self-care lessons which would be integrated in the CFE classes.

XI. Significance of the Study

The study, which aimed at surfacing the pre-service educators' pandemic experiences and self-care activities, were significant to the following:

School Administration. The findings of the study would provide feedback as to state of health of the pre-service educators which would serve as bases for the crafting of school-based intervention programs that will address these concerns.

Faculty and Staff. Findings of the study would provide them information on the pandemic experiences of pre-service educators which they can use to promote the students' wellbeing.

Parents. The findings would provide them information as to the pandemic experiences of their children, monitor them, and make necessary actions to address these concerns.

Students. The students would be guided in terms of self-care activities which will help them make right decisions and actions in their life.

Future Researchers. The study would provide relevant references as bases for future related studies along these topics.

XII. Definition of Terms

The following terms are conceptually and operationally defined in this study:

Pandemic experiences in this study refers to the pre-service educators' state of wellbeing specifically in terms of how they were feeling at present amidst the lockdown and quarantine protocols.

Problems encountered refers to the challenges the pre-service educators have encountered in terms of personal, educational, and family aspects.

Self-care activities refers to the actions the students had undertaken to respond to their needs and concerns.

XIII. Review of Related Literature and Studies

Adolescence is a distinct stage of human life characterized by rapid physical and psychological changes and which may lead to confusion, tension, frustrations and feeling of insecurity. It is a period of transition where they are striving to achieve autonomy and identity. Adolescent's experiences conflict between himself and society and even within himself (Shivarajan, 2008). In the period of transition, an individual is neither a child nor an adult and the changes of the role in society, shattered relations in

home, failure to decide his/her role in social setting, difficulty in adjusting with others, especially opposite sex, unnecessary restriction on movement make them under psychological stress. Adolescent period of life is considered as in the period of stress and strain, storm and strife. During this period emotions fluctuate very frequently and quickly. Physical and psychological changes result in restlessness, broken relationships, moody, emotionally perturbed and touchy. This is a time when individuals striving to wean themselves away from family in order to become self-sufficient and independent. These internal conflicts make the adolescence to be easily precipitated by peer pressure, may take drugs or get addicted to alcohol, other deviance, delinquency and emotional and behavioral problems. The contemporary health problems in adolescence are linked to changing lifestyle and having significant correlation with psychological well-being. Adolescents' risk taking behaviors significantly contribute to the morbidity and mortality of this group (Nair, 2004). This high risk behavior of adolescence includes poor safety measures, unsafe sexual behavior, substance abuse, violence and suicide.

Mental Health Impact of Quarantine and Isolation

News about Corona Virus cases in China started coming in December, 2019. Pandey (2020) stated that at first, people in other countries were mostly in denial that the corona virus will not affect them. However, the cases started to increase and take the form of epidemic and gradually other countries have been affected by it. Panic and worry spread among individuals. The highly infective virus soon took the form of a pandemic which alarmed many countries and became a significant public health concern (Pandey, 2020).

The Corona viruses responsible for this public menace belong to a group of RNA viruses, which causes diseases in mammals and birds. In humans, predominantly, it causes mild to lethal respiratory tract infections. Lethal varieties of these viral infections are Sub-acute respiratory Syndrome (SARS), Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), and Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). The history of human coronaviruses began in 1965 when Tyrrell and Bynoe found that they could passage a virus named B814 from human organ culture, isolated from a person having respiratory tract infection. Later with work of Tyrell and other scientists a new group of viruses named coronavirus (corona denoting in Latin a crown-like appearance, of the surface projections) came into being, officially accepted as a new genus of viruses. This is not the first time world has been affected by epidemics and pandemics. The world over a period of thousands of year has seen many pandemics. During the 18th and 19th century pandemic of Cholera, plague, typhoid, Small pox, HIV AIDS (Ongoing Pandemic) and yellow fever has been seen. Sub-acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) epidemic affected many parts of the world during 2002-2004, and then the swine flu epidemic of 2009 (Pandey, 2020).

The Spread of COVID-19

With the spread of Covid-19 globally, countries have taken several measures to contain it. Isolation, quarantine and lockdown rigorously are the most difficult yet necessary step. Quarantine and Isolation are methods to stop the spread of an infective illness. Quarantine means separation of an individual from others and community, who has any exposure to known infected person with that infection. The disease may or may not be evident in a quarantined individual. Isolation word although used interchangeably with quarantine in stricter sense is applied to restriction of movement of Infected person in whom the disease is evident. Quarantine and Isolation have been used for persons who had travelled internationally recently and for those individuals who had come in contact with persons declared to be COVID 19 positive which includes family members and others who had significant exposure with infected person in the last few weeks before their illness was known.

The news of epidemic spread is a significant stress for most especially for those Individual who have to undergo quarantine and isolation. Quarantine and Isolation can be of three types. First is the home based- self quarantine which is considered slightly better than others as it may provide the individual the comfort of their homes. However, if stringent methods are not followed adequately, the very purpose of quarantine may be defeated. Home based quarantine puts the responsibility entirely on an individual to save themselves, family members and the entire community from spread of the illness. However for those individuals where home isolation is not possible due to lack of space for e.g. slum areas or due lack of knowledge and understanding of the various measures, hospital based quarantine is done providing the individual with their basic needs.

Camp based quarantine is also being followed for selected cases like on duty doctors and migrant laborers where large number makes it impossible to provide accommodation in hospitals. Quarantine can

be imposed based on current laws or it can be self-motivated by responsible individuals. The stress of going into quarantine like other stresses may present differently in different individuals depending on their coping skills, personality factors and pre-morbid functioning. The distress of going into quarantine may lead to acute stress disorders. Quarantined individual may report feeling exhausted, bored, detached, irritable, anxious, sleep disturbance, low mood. Many of these symptoms may be short lasting for the period of quarantine while for others, these may be long lasting and may require follow up care to deal with emerging psychiatric disorders.

COVID-19 pandemic has led world to a standstill. Quarantine and Isolation are a must to contain the viral spread. This has led to newer challenges for the psychiatrist and other mental health professionals world wide. The quarantine period is extremely critical from a psychiatric view point as the affected individual may not only be exposed to psychological problems during but also after it. The psychiatrist must take into the consideration the various psychological morbidities associated with it and should tackle them accordingly to provide effective health care.

Child and Adolescent Mental Health during the Pandemic Lockdown

Yadav and Srivastava (2020) indicated that the pandemic lockdown has brought all people into a very crucial time. It is affecting adults and older people especially children and adolescents. The pandemic is affecting children and adolescents physically and mentally and makes them vulnerable to various problems. Parents play a vital role in helping children and adolescents during this tough time. Parents must exercise patience, empathy, non- judgment, and supportiveness and make them cope up with this time with ease. Due to the nationwide lockdown, all the schools and institutions have been closed. There is a sudden change in the environment of the children who are staying with their parents or any caregiver as their outdoor activities and social interaction with friends have been restricted. Some have been separated from their caregivers due to being infected or suspected from the virus. Some of them are under the care of charity groups whose caregivers are infected or have died. Children are most susceptible to various mental health problems. Due to this lockdown many children are suffering. This is evident in the significant changes that occurred in a child's routine life and social infrastructure.

Mental health problems can broadly be evident as fear of infection, irritability , boredom, anxiety, stress, depression, unhealthy sleeping and eating habits, difficulty in attention and concentration. What can be done to help the children? Children must be provided with clear information about the pandemic in order to reduce anxiety and fear, but limit the use of social media and news. Parents and caregivers must be supportive and empathic to the child. Parents and caregivers must engage them in activities like crafts from waste papers, dancing, singing, board games and others to make them calm and relieved. A daily time-table can be made wherein children can be asked to follow it regularly. Schedule the study hours, if preferable, during their school timings. Physical activities and exercises with the help of some online videos at home are also helpful to improve sleeping and eating habits. During this crucial time, it is necessary for all of us to be calm and supportive for those suffering in this lockdown phase. Be it our family or our friends, we should spread awareness and try to make the situation lighter for them, instead of just stressing them out or leaving them alone (Yadav and Srivastava, 2020).

Common Mental Health Problems during COVID -19 Pandemic

Prakash and Gupta (2020) reported that people's anxious reactions trigger public disruptive behaviors as people rush to stores, health centers, and pharmacies and health supply become scarce and the country health care service provision is affected. Evidence also suggests that individuals may experience symptoms of psychosis, anxiety, trauma, suicidal ideation, and panic during outbreaks of communicable diseases. Anxiety is a facilitator of decreased immune response to infection and further increases the severity of the disease.

The need for social distancing was immense and the various world leaders were quick to pass stringent lockdowns in most parts of the world. Various stressors have culminated to breakdown in normal functioning of the individuals. Loss of jobs, increased financial strain, rising prices of goods for consumption, uncertainty regarding academic sessions and the most important that is fear of the disease have all put a person across the limits of his psychological wellbeing. Data from ILO suggests a significant decline in jobs in the year of 2020, i.e. around 25 millions. With health and financial security playing on our minds, home schooling stress, concerned about the welfare of our family and friends and frustration at being stuck in the house, it is fair to say most of our tolerance levels are low. With the lack

of standard and specific treatment protocol for COVID-19 the uncertainty looms large among the kin of the affected individuals. Contrary to other infections COVID 19 presents a variable course of illness. These above factors have increased unprecedented stress among masses (Prakash and Gupta, 2020).

Problems in people with Mental illness due to COVID 19

Anxiety disorders may arise as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and country-wide lockdown. It may also cause exacerbation of symptoms in diagnosed cases. Any simple flu like symptom increases anxiety due to COVID-19. As the symptoms of various flu like disorders overlap among themselves, a slight cough can create a sense of doom among people. The depiction and exaggeration of the current situation in the media has led to a panic like situation which is doing more harm than good.

Obsessive Compulsive Disorder patients, especially those who have checking, hoarding and washing compulsion, are at higher risk. Abnormal becomes the new normal for people who have washing compulsions and fear of contamination. Advice on improving personal hygiene measures might increase the contamination obsessions and washing compulsions. In the face of ongoing lockdown, patients are more likely to resort to panic buying and excessive hoarding of essential items, even though continuous supply of essential items is assured by the government.

For recurrent depressive disorder patients, lockdown is a major stress threatening normal daily routine, social rhythm and thereby increasing stress levels, which would further escalate the cortisol level, resulting in a vicious exacerbation of depressive symptoms. Inability to join work, dwindling finances and the long term impact on economy will have its effect on new and pre-existing depressive illnesses. In a person with a previous psychiatric disorder, all these problems can surface with renewed severity and can lead to PTSD or even suicidal thoughts and attempts.

For substance use disorder patients, this period could be lethal as nonavailability of substance or medicines can precipitate severe withdrawal symptoms and medical emergencies like delirium or seizures, which can be life-threatening due to inadequate accessibility to dwindling emergency services .

Patients with bipolar disorder and schizophrenia are likely to have relapses due to risk in both the availability of regular medication and medication compliance. Anxiety can be so overwhelming, that it can precipitate paranoia and nihilistic delusions.

A staggering number of suicides, caused by fear of infection, loneliness, lack of freedom of movement, and alcohol withdrawal during lockdown has also increased.

Coping during the Lockdown

Each person has a unique style of coping and adjusting. The emotional impact of an emergency on a person can depend on the person's characteristics, resilience, and adjustment. Social and economic circumstances of the person and their community compatibility, availability of local resources all determine the amount of adjustment an individual can have.

Individuals must realize that there are certain things which we cannot control. Concern and worry are natural but these will merely aggravate the situation. The infection is likely to spread through the population in unpredictable ways. There is nothing one can do about this but if one follows precautions, one is less likely to get sick. There is some benefit to planning. One needs to move on and focus on living life rather than worrying about the virus. One can try to control other people's reactions by listening and helping people work through the facts concerning the virus. Lastly, it is helpful to keep in touch with a health care provider if stress reactions interfere with one's daily activities for several days in a row.

Impact of Mental Health on Academic Performance of Students During COVID-19 Lockdown

Singh and Yadav (2020) remarked that education has been defined as a process of including progressive or desirable change in a person as a results of teaching and study (English and English 1958) and systematic instruction, schooling or training given to the young (and by extension to the adults) in preparation for the work of life (Oxford univ. dictionary 1955).

Academic performance is the extent to which students, teachers or institutions have attained their short or long term educational goals. Academic achievement is commonly measured through

examination and assessments. Several factors affect academic performance. Personal factors include sensation and perception, fatigue and boredom, age and maturation, emotional condition, needs, interests, motivation, attention, intelligence, aptitude, attitude etc. Psychosocial factors arise from cultural environment, community, family, organization, society, media, technology, religion, ideology, language, and communication which influence the individual to think and act in a certain way. In terms of environmental factors, the family is the primary and most significant environment in which a student is exposed. Family plays an important role in students' academic performance. Family cultural resources and environment determine the child's academic performances. Participation of parents in education and learning behaviors and achievements affect the academic performance. Socio-demography of a family can affect the academic performances. Change in family circumstance, conflicts, stress load, substance abuse by any family member, lack trust can affect the academic performance (Singh and Yadav, 2020).

Moreover, teaching and school environment play an important role in shaping the behavior of students. The way they manage and teach produces effects on academic performances in natural surroundings. Psychosocial, environmental and personal factors affect the students' academic performance of students. Students have been affected by closure of their schools, colleges, universities and other educational institutions in many countries. Most of board examinations were postponed. The biggest challenge to the students is the dilemma about the future in terms of their promotion to next class/ courses and academic future. Many schools, colleges, and institutions started e-learning. However, major questions have arisen for those students who do not have laptops and internet facilities at home. Added to these difficulties is the fact that some courses, such as labs, fine arts, clerkship, dance, art, and music, cannot be taught online. Further, the worldwide rapid increase of infected cases has created a sense of uncertainty about future and has led to anxiety about the end result about the outcome. It has also caused significant increases in stress, anxiety, emotional breakdown and internet addiction among the school/ college and university students. These can lead to unfavorable effects on the learning and psychological health of students. Students have also been observed to be spending undue time on the social media and electronic gadgets. The COVID-19 pandemic has forced countries to address three emergencies at the same time: health, social and economic emergencies. These emergencies further exacerbate the academic problem in students (Singh and Yadav, 2020).

Prevention and resilience

Persons who are practicing social distancing and sanitization will not get COVID-19; though among those who do get infected, the majority will not need hospital level care; and the majority of those who are hospitalized will survive. Physical exercise, taking balanced diet and good sleep are important factors for self-care because poor quality of sleep is predictor of emotional distress. In research, it has been found simply helping individuals to sleep properly is proving to be as effective as treatment for depression as antidepressant. Regarding care of students and their academic performance special attention is needed in the form of life skills education, e-learning, families, social supports, strengthen emotional health by (exercise, sleep, relaxation, healthy eating), motivation sharing of feelings, writing, music, telecounseling by specialist health workers.

In response to children's physical and mental needs during the COVID-19 outbreak, Zhang, Gui, Xu, Zhu, Zhai, Ge, and Xu (2020) initiated a project entitled the Child Health Initiative for Children and Adolescents (CHI) which was launched to provide multidisciplinary support and services on physical and mental health, to perform health communication, and to relieve anxiety and stress. It is an internet-based interactive platform for children and adolescents intended to improve their overall well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. The platform includes different dimensions, such as disease prevention and treatment, child health communication and science popularization, improvement of children's mental health, and increment of family and community cohesion. In addition, the platform is keeping updated the latest COVID-19 pandemic information for helping to relieve anxiety and stress in children and parents. It also informs users of child health management, healthy physical growth, and mental health improvement in various forms, such as text, pictures, videos, audiobooks, and webinars.

Family Dynamics during Lockdown

Jaishy and Pandey (2020) stated that in the wake of the covid19 pandemic a need has arisen to decipher the underlying impact of lockdown and isolation on the functioning of a family. The family performs a variety of functions in human society. The interactions among the family members and its role in the development of modern human society has been immense. The new world order created by the

pandemic has threatened to disrupt the well maintained social fabric and family unit as a whole. Family dynamics are the pattern of relating, or interactions between family members. Each family system and its dynamics are unique, although there are some common patterns. Having a close-knit and supportive family provides emotional support, economic wellbeing, and increases overall health. This unprecedented event of lockdown has extended for a prolonged period of time. People who were never accustomed to spending much time in home now are forced to stay in self isolation or quarantine for their own safety and greater cause to flatten the pandemic curve.

The lockdown due to corona virus has brought a host of new pressures and challenges to our everyday family life. The Covid -19 crisis means many people are feeling overwhelmed. Excessive levels of familial conflicts and reports of domestic violence and child abuse has grown manifold. Pandemics are a form of external stress for couples and families specially for those who are more severely affected (e.g. those who develop the disease, become unemployed, experience major financial losses).

Communication among family members has grown with the rise of multimedia technology like video calling apps. Some of the steps that can be taken by family members to maintain happy family relationships during lockdown include good communication skills among family members. Families that practice positive communication express appreciation and gratitude for one another. They are able to compromise, and to have fun and laugh with one another. Moreover, families should also practice the virtue of pardoning oneself and others. In this unprecedented times, there is no right or wrong way to be (Jaishy and Pandey, 2020).

Family members should agree to ease off one another. A productive routine should be maintained at this time. In this challenging time of social distancing and isolation, one may slip into not getting properly dressed ,not having meals on time ,disturbances in sleeping pattern .These factors lead to stressful personal conditions eventually leading to difficulties in the family setting. A defined morning routine, taking meals on time, exercises, meditation, and end point to a day's activity may be precisely devised.

If any deviant behavior is noticeable, family members should reach out, sit down and talk. Solving strategies to ameliorate unhealthy behaviors can lead to a fruitful time in the house. There is always a need for assistance when personal capabilities have been squeezed out. Asking help from mental health professionals and psychiatrist may help in dire situations and help fulfill a person's role in a family. Finally we all should acknowledge that we are stuck. Lockdown is an opportunity to do something differently .Everyone is sequestered together at home and this tends to put a spotlight on what is, and is not, working with in your relationship and family dynamics (Jaishy and Pandey, 2020).

Social Media and its Impact on Mental Health

As defined in the article of Singh (2020), social media refers to websites and applications that enable users to create and share content or to participate in social networking. There are about 3.81 billion social media users around the world. More than 63% of eligible population is already on social media, spending on an average, two and half hours using social media each day. Human beings are social creatures. We need social relationship, companionship and validity of others to thrive in life and the strength of our connections has a huge impact on our mental health and happiness. At this time of lockdowns, social distancing and isolation, social media can be an invaluable tool for keeping us in touch with friends, loved ones, and the wider world. Being socially connected to others can ease our distress, boost self- esteem, prevent loneliness and provide comfort and joy. On the flip side, lacking strong social connections can pose a serious threat to our mental and emotional health. It's important to remember that social media can never be a replacement for real world human connection, spending too much time engaging with social media can actually make us feel more lonely and isolated and exacerbate mental health problems such as anxiety and depression. We should also be careful about fake news circulating on social media, always check its authenticity before forwarding to someone else. Always check reputable news sources before believing or forwarding any rumors about COVID-19 that may cause panic

Positive aspects of social media

Singh (2020) indicated that social media is an easier and cheaper way to communicate and stay up to date with family and friends around the world. We not only know about different events happening in our friend's life, we can also express our emotions through social media. It increase the sense of

interconnectedness and social closeness. Further, social media help as find new friends and communities and network with other people who share similar interests or ambitions.

At this time of lockdowns, social distancing and isolation, social media can be good medium to seek and provide emotional support. It provide vital social connection to people living in a remote area, for example, or having limited independence, social anxiety, or are part of a marginalized group. People are increasingly relying on social media platforms to express themselves positively and accurately. Social media provide an outlet to teenagers to express themselves, which is important because expression is key during teenage years. Lockdown has inspired people to be creative and carry out their hobbies of cooking, singing, gardening etc. social medial has provided them platform to share their creativity.

Social media helps to promote worthwhile causes and raise awareness on important issues like social distancing and use of mask to prevent COVID infection. Social media, if used carefully, can be sources of valuable information and learning. During lockdowns, various school and colleges are teaching and sharing academic materials through social media.

Negative aspects of social media

Social media tend to promoting negative emotions. Even if we know that images we are viewing on social media are manipulated, they can still make us feel insecure about how we look or what's going on in our own life. Similarly, we are all aware that other people tend to share just the highlights of their lives, rarely the low points that everyone experiences. But that does not lessen those feelings of envy and dissatisfaction when we are scrolling through a friend's airbrushed photos of their tropical beach holiday or reading about their exciting new promotion at work. Social media seem to exacerbate feelings that others are having more fun or living better lives than us. Fear of missing out (FOMO) on certain things can impact our self-esteem, trigger anxiety, and fuel even greater social media use. It can compel us to pick up our phone every few minutes to check for updates, or compulsively respond to each and every alert even if that means taking risks while we are driving, missing out on sleep at night, or prioritizing social media interaction over real world relationships.

Another negative aspect is self-absorption. Sharing endless "selfies" and all your innermost thoughts on social media can create an unhealthy self-centeredness and distance you from real-life connections. Cyber bullying is extremely common these days, many teens report being bullied on social media and many other users are subjected to offensive comments. Social media platforms can be hotspots for spreading hurtful rumors, lies and abuse that can leave lasting emotional scars. Victims of cyber bullying suffer from bouts of depression, anxiety, Suicidal tendencies, low self-esteem, anger and frustration. Social media addiction is a behavioral addiction characterized by uncontrollable urge to use social media and devoting so much time and effort to social media that it impairs other important life areas. Excessive social media have detrimental effect over mental health and can cause insomnia, memory problem, anxiety and depression.

Impact of Lockdowns on Social Media Use

Use of social media has increased many folds during current lockdowns due to various obvious reasons Lockdown increased loneliness and boredom. Using social media more often increased FOMO, inadequacy, dissatisfaction. Negative effect on mood worsens symptoms of stress, anxiety and depression. In the use of social media, we should be careful as it can lead to excessive use. This can lead to negativity which is self-perpetuating vicious cycle of unhealthy social media use.

The following are indicators that social media may be adversely affecting an individual's mental health: 1) Spending more time on social media than with real world friends and family members; 2) Comparing yourself unfavorably with others on social media; 3) Pressure to post regular content about yourself, get comments or likes on your posts, or respond quickly and enthusiastically to friends' posts; 4) Engaging in risky behavior in order to gain likes, shares, or positive reactions on social media; 5) Suffering from sleep problems; 6) Rather than helping to alleviate negative feelings and boost your mood, you feel more anxious, depressed, or lonely after using social media; 7) Experiencing cyber bullying or you worry that you have no control over the things people post about you; 8) Every spare moment is filled by engaging with social media, leaving you little or no time for reflecting on who you are, what you think; and, 9) Checking social media while in important meeting or family gatherings (Singh, 2020).

Many individuals access social media purely out of habit or to mindlessly kill moments of downtime. But by focusing on one's motivation for logging on, the time spent on social media will not only be reduced, it will also improve one's experience and avoid many of the negative aspects. More quality time must be spent with family and offline friends. Time for self-reflection is necessary. Feeling and expressing gratitude about the important things in one's life can be a welcome relief to the resentment, animosity, and discontent sometimes generated by social media. Lastly, the practice of mindfulness is also beneficial to one's mental health.

Social media if used carefully can help us to stay connected with our friend and family in this time of lockdown. It can be a source of emotional and social support at time of need. If use of social media make us happy, boost our self-esteem it can have positive impact on our mental health but if we have feeling of missing out, self-doubt, and disappointment after using social media we should check our time on social media.

Synthesis

The present global pandemic had brought innumerable issues to everyone particularly the youth of today. The government has imposed quarantine and isolation which had greatly affected the youth's mental health. Children and adolescents' mental health during the pandemic crisis should be addressed. Parents, caregivers, and other concerned agencies and institutions must work hand in hand to help these individuals maintain their wellbeing. Studies conducted by Prakash and Gupta (2020), Singh and Yadav (2020), and Zhang, Gui, Xu, Zhu, Zhai, Ge, and Xu (2020) focused on the effects of pandemic on the physical and mental health of children and adolescents. The studies of Jaishy and Pandey (2020) determined family dynamics during lockdown and Singh (2020) studied the impact of social media on mental health. The present study, however, surfaced the pandemic experiences of the pre-service educators in terms of their perceived mental health status, problems they had encountered in terms of personal, educational, and family concerns as well as self-care activities they had been doing to maintain wellbeing.

XIV. Research Methodology

Research Design

This study is a qualitative research which made use of written interview guide questions that were lifted from the webinar series of the World Health Organization (WHO) Office of the Secretary-General's Envoy on Youth . The Secretary-General's Envoy on Youth, in partnership with the World Health Organisation and UNICEF, hosted a series of webinars for young people, titled "#CopingWithCOVID" which aimed to provide young people with a platform for genuine connection amid uncertainty, encouraging them to field their questions to the experts from UNICEF and WHO, generate mental health awareness among young people, and strengthen demand for integrated mental health and psychosocial interventions.

A. Research Environment

The study was conducted at St. Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya one of the five CICM schools in the Philippines founded in 1928 and earned its university status in 1994. Saint Mary's University was chosen as the locale of the study considering the richness of the environment and the ease of gathering data. In addition, the university also has guidance counselors who shepherd and assist students in ensuring their wellbeing in aspects concerning studies, families, relationships, specifically their mental wellbeing amidst the pandemic on covid-19.

B. Research Instrument

The research tool used in gathering data were the four guide questions which were lifted from the webinar series of the World Health Organization (WHO) Office of the Secretary-General's Envoy on Youth. The said four guide questions were the focus of the discussion in the webinar series.

C. Sampling Procedure and Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the pre-service educators who were taking up CFE 101 and CFE 104 classes. Purposive sampling was used in the selection of the respondents.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

This study aimed to surface the pre-service educators' pandemic experiences. Written interview guide questions were posted in the Learning Management System (LMS) of the respective classes during the first term of the first semester, SY 2020-2021. The students in these classes were asked to answer the written guide questions. The students were given one week to answer the questions. After a week, the students' responses were downloaded. The responses were coded and arranged thematically.

XV. Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

A. Pre-service Educators' Perceived Mental Health Status Amidst the Pandemic Crisis

Table 1. Pre-service Educators' Perceived Mental Health Status Amidst the Pandemic Crisis

Perceived Mental Health Status	Frequency	%
Frustrated (feeling discouragement, anger, and annoyance because of unresolved problems or unfulfilled goals, desires, or needs)	27	54
Stressed (feeling of bodily or mental tension caused by physical, chemical, or emotional factor)	15	30
Anxious (feeling or showing uncomfortable feelings of uncertainty)	13	26
Grateful (feeling or expressing gratitude)	8	16

The table shows the pre-service educators' perceived mental health status amidst the pandemic crisis. As shown in the table, foremost among the reported mental health status among pre-service educators was they felt frustrated (27), followed by feeling stressed (15), and anxious (13), although eight of them mentioned feeling grateful.

This finding is corroborated by the study of Tee, Tee, Anlacan, Aligam, Reyes, Kuruchittham, and Ho (2020) which stated that recent imposed quarantine by the health authority, prolonged stay at home, poor self-reported health status, feeling of too much unnecessary worry has been made about COVID-19, concerns about family members getting sick, and feeling of being discriminated by other countries were associated with a greater psychological impact of the pandemic and higher levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. Liu, Zhang, Wong, and Hyun (2020) also stated that young adults face major psychological challenges such as stress in managing school or work responsibilities during this time while having no sense of certainty regarding the pandemic's end. Feeling cut off from social groups may lead one to feel vulnerable and pessimistic about one's circumstances, altogether producing negative mood states and anxiety that are further heightened during a pandemic. Moreover, the study of Dvorsky, Breaux, and Becker (2020) reported that Chinese adolescents have experienced very high rates of anxiety and depression during the COVID-19 outbreak.

Verbatim responses indicated that the pre-service educators felt frustrated amidst the present pandemic crises. As Student A reported in terms of how he felt regarding online classes, "It's hard to cope hard to cope up because the connection is poor. It's really frustrating" This was seconded by Student B who stated, "I don't have the encouragement to do things because there are so much to do to comply to one subject". Moreover, Student C indicated that she felt "heavy feelings of sadness, disappointment, and pain in the past months and weeks" because of the events that "I wasn't prepared to face". Other students reported feeling of "boredom and irritability" because some of their plans were "wasted and postponed".

Feelings of being anxious were also reported by the pre-service educators. Student C mentioned, "I am worried about the cases we have here in our country, because as time goes by it is getting bigger and it seems like the government doesn't care about it that much". This was corroborated by Student D who reported "feeling anxious about the rising numbers of the COVID - 19 in the province", Student E who stated, "...worried about our health and situation right now because we don't know where are the virus. Also I am worried that this situation will get worse." Other students mentioned "feeling troubled, thinking of my future", "feeling anxious about the rising numbers of the COVID - 19 in the province", "feeling scared, anxious and worried", and "feeling of fear and many "what if" thoughts".

Stress is a physiological response connected to an external event. During this pandemic, the pre-service educators reported feelings of "being physically and mentally drained" and "Feeling pressured with acads". This was affirmed by Student F who mentioned that this pandemic crisis makes her feel

“distressed so much to the extent that it is little by little affecting my mental health”. Student G also verbalized, “I am stressed at times and I also feel emptiness during this pandemic”

Though many students reported negative feelings in this pandemic crisis, it is noteworthy to mention that a number of students manifested positivity amidst the pandemic crisis. As attested by Student H, “I am happy and I feel like I am lucky because despite of this pandemic, my parents still manage to enroll me in school and provide my needs”. Student I stated, “I feel okay and grateful because I can still manage to attend my online classes and I am thankful that God always bless me and my family because we are still healthy”. Moreover, Student J indicated, “I still feel blessed despite of the Covid 19 for I know God allows this to happen not to weaken us but to strengthen our faith and find our hope in Him. I feel blessed because God guides and protects me and my family”. Student K also felt grateful as she stated, “This pandemic made me and my father spend time and bond with each other”.

These perceived mental health status reported by the pre-service educators imply the severity of experiences of young adults during the pandemic which indicates numerous mental health concerns.

B. Problems Encountered by the Pre-Service Educators amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic

Table 2. Problems encountered by the pre-service educators in terms of personal concerns

Personal concerns	Frequency	%
1. Physical and mental health problems (anxiety, overthinking, depression)	25	50
2. Loss of social interaction	11	22
4. Changes in lifestyle (eating and sleeping patterns, exercise)	10	20
3. Quarantine / travel restrictions	8	16

The table shows that foremost among the problems encountered by pre-service educators in terms of personal concerns was mental health problems (46%), followed by loss of social interaction (22%), changes in lifestyle (20%), and quarantine/travel restrictions (16%).

This finding is corroborated in the study of Xie, Xue, Zhou, Zhu, Liu, Zhang, and Sineong (2020) which indicated that students reported having depressive and anxiety symptoms.

Verbatim reports from the pre-service educators showed students encountered problems amidst the pandemic crisis such as physical and mental and health problems. Specifically, Student L stated, “I struggle from various personal issues and I don’t have the outlet to at least ease my frustrations since I cannot be with my friends or go to places that I want”. Other students mentioned “overthinking, depression, and anxiety” because “fighting an enemy which is not visible is scary”. Student M also reported, “I hardly control my emotions, and I feel like I want cry anytime I feel like I want to and I don’t even know the reason behind it”. Student N also mentioned experiencing “sudden loss of determination to do the usual things in a new and different way”. Moreover, Student O also stated “...even though I rest, I feel like I am not resting at all”.

The pre-service educators also mentioned personal concerns such as loss of social interaction. As Student P indicated, “I don’t like being stuck at home like I am imprisoned in my own house”. Students reported that “lack of connectivity” prevented them “to socialize with other people physically” and they felt sad because they “seldom see their friends whom they want to hang out with” and “there are planned activities in our youth ministry that are not allowed due to social distancing”.

Due to the safety measures enforced by authorities such as lockdown and quarantine, lifestyles of many people have changes such as eating habits, sleeping patterns and exercise. Student Q mentioned, “Since we are stuck in our houses, we tend to relax and be less active on things that can be important entirely for our growth and development as a person”. As affirmed by Student R, “Because of the lockdown I can’t get to have a proper exercise that I usually do like biking, jogging and many more”. Other students mentioned “worrying about health” because they “... don’t eat meals on the right time” “difficulties in sleeping (insomnia), my body clock is so bad” and “lack of sleep because of the loaded activities and projects”.

Quarantine and travel restrictions were also personal problems encountered by the pre-service educators. Student S reported “I have been struggling to search out ways to tolerate lodge in home orders”. Student T also mentioned “I felt that I am in a jail or in a cage which I am getting fatigue because

of less workout, walking and others". Other students mentioned "less access to things outside our municipality" because "we could not go out without a pass".

Table 3. Problems encountered by the pre-service educators in terms of educational concerns

Educational Concerns	f	%
1. Poor internet connectivity and power interruption	14	28
2. Difficulty in online class	13	26
4. No gadgets/lack of resources	2	5

As indicated in the table, in terms of educational concerns, foremost among the pre-service educators problems was poor internet connectivity and power interruption (24%), followed by difficulty in online class (26%), no gadgets or lack of resources (5%).

This is affirmed in the study conducted by Dhawan (2020) which found that difficulties and problems associated with modern technology range from downloading errors, issues with installation, login problems, problems with audio and video, and so on.

This is corroborated in the verbatim responses of pre-service educators. Student U reported, "The status of the internet connection in our place is very poor and unstable" and "the threat of brownout". Student V also mentioned "I feel so stressed because I wasn't able to submit my activities due to power interruption".

Moreover, the students also struggled with the difficulties of online classes. As Student W stated, "I do not know how long I could take this kind of educational system". Other students mentioned other challenges such as "adjusting to this new mode of learning", "struggle in the demands of online class" because "teachers are only giving lots of modules that are hard to understand" and "unlimited number of requirements". Further, Student W also mentioned, "It is hard for me to study online since I do not have the right resources".

Table 4. Problems encountered by the pre-service educators in terms of family concerns

Family concerns	f	%
1. Financial problem	13	26
3. Family issues	2	4

As indicated in Table 4, family concerns involving financial problem (26%) and family issues (4%) were encountered by the pre-service educators.

Similarly, Nicola, Alsafi, Sohrabi, Kerwan, Al-Jabir, Iosifidis, and Agha (2020) indicated that the socio-economic implications of covid -19 pandemic involves reduced workforce across all economic sectors and caused many jobs to be lost.

Verbatim responses from the pre-service educators affirmed these findings, As reported by Student X, "we don't even know how to make money for our living because the salary of my parents and siblings are not enough and sufficient". Student Y also mentioned "financially unstable because my father is being locked down for six months". Student Y also remarked, " I have many priorities at home and sometimes while I am having classes like in google meet, I am doing household chores and I cannot focus". Other students mentioned "family issues and problems".

Parents are essential to buffering their children's stresses, helping them to manage their feelings and make sense of their own experiences. However, this buffering requires a parent who is sufficiently emotionally and physically resourced to do so. With parents increasingly experiencing their own demoralizing losses such as lost jobs, their ability to buffer their children's stresses inevitably diminishes over time, increasing the risk that this pandemic becomes traumatic for children and youth, with enduring emotional consequences (Courtney, Watson, Battaglia, Mulsant, and Szatmari, 2020; Oosterhoff, Palmer, Wilson, and Shook, 2020).

Table 5. Pre-service educators' Reported Self-Care Activities for their Physical and Mental Wellbeing amidst the Pandemic Crisis

Suggested activities	f	%
1. Having a proper diet and personal hygiene	34	68
2. Having enough sleep and rest	31	62
3. Making time to unwind and doing the things that make you happy and grow	28	56
4. Communicating with family and friends	26	52
5. Praying and meditating	24	48
6. Doing exercise	19	38
7. Being positive and avoiding negative thoughts and actions	11	22
8. Following safety protocols	5	10
9. Developing new skills	2	4

Table 5 shows the pre-service educators' self-care activities for their physical and mental wellbeing amidst the pandemic crisis. Foremost among these reported self-care activities was Having a proper diet and personal hygiene (68%), followed by Having enough sleep and rest (62%), making time to unwind and doing the things that make you happy and grow (56%), communicating with family and friends (52%), praying and meditating (48%), doing exercise (38%), and being positive and avoiding negative thoughts and actions. The least among these reported self-care activities were developing new skills (4%) and following safety protocols (10%).

This finding is affirmed in the study conducted by Dvorsky, Breaux, and Becker (2020) which found that close relationships with competent and caring adults such as family members and peers have an important role in nurturing the growth, stability, and recovery of self-regulation, learning, problem-solving, motivation to adapt, persistence, and hope. In the midst of a global pandemic, children and adolescents depend on the resilience of these interdependent systems.

Verbatim responses from the pre-service educators affirm these findings. They recognize the importance of having a proper diet and maintaining personal hygiene. As Student AA mentioned, "I eat healthy foods and drink water to make myself hydrated". Student BB rejoined, "I stay hydrated, eat vegetables to make my body strong and healthy". Other students mentioned having "good and proper hygiene", "good rest", "sleep at least 7-8 hours a day".

The pre-service educators have also explored ways to maintain physical and mental wellbeing by finding time to unwind and doing things that make them happy and grow. Student CC reported "having a break from the stress like eating, listening to music, and watching my favorite youtubers". Student DD also mentioned, "I treat myself spiritually (reading moral stories), emotionally (doing things I want), physically (exercising), and mentally (watching films that interest me)". Other students stated "doing stuffs that interests me and motivates me", "doing things that would holistically help me as a person such as relax and enjoy what I wanted to do", "relaxing and enjoying your hobbies", "posting tweets to express my feelings", "dancing just to release negative vibe", "singing a song in a high volume to release stress", "stimulating the mind such as reading books, magazines, or doing puzzles that can exercise the brain is also vital for cognitive development", "listening to music", "reading materials on coping mechanism", and "watching inspiring videos".

The pre-service educators also recognize the importance of communicating with family and friends. Student EE mentioned, "I just need to talk to people I am comfortable to be with, who can understand what I am going through and a continuous assurance that everything will be okay". Student FF rejoined, "I surround myself with the right people whom I could lean on whenever I am with my darkest moments". Student GG also stated, "I do not isolate myself so that my social life will be active and it would also help me to prevent myself from overthinking and such". Other students reported "the need to speak out and share it to others, someone to talk to", and "spending time with friends, loved ones and people you trust, but it must a proper way, we can also talk about or express your feelings regularly", "sharing problems with my friends through messenger/videocall", "always keeping in touch

with my friends who makes me happy”, and “surrounding myself with people who are good and has a positive vibe that can impact how I live such as my family and friends”.

The pre-service educators also pray and meditate to maintain a holistic wellbeing. As stated by Student HH, “I reflect and meditate first before saying or doing something”. Student II also mentioned, “I pray to God because He is the one who make us strength”. Student JJ the need “to have a strong faith to God that will serve as our foundation to attain personal and mental well-being because faith results to hope and hope results to positivity then positivity results to joy”. Other students reported that what they “need the most is the presence of Almighty God”, “in these trying times, they did not forget to pray always”, and “being in touch and having a close relationship to our Almighty”.

Moreover, the pre-service educators also recognize the importance of being positive and avoiding negative thoughts and actions. Student KK stated, “I focus more on ourselves and believe that we can make it through”. Student LL also pointed the need to “diminish toxic factors such as mitigating destructive habits, eradicating procrastination, and to think positive and look at the brighter side of the future”. Other students mentioned the importance of “understanding myself and be able to maintain it by enhancing my strengths and develop my weaknesses”, “being optimistic”, “focus on self – care and self – assessment of the things I made”, “don’t drink alcoholic beverages”, “avoid illicit drug use”, “manage my emotions well”, and avoid overthinking and only focus on positive thing”.

Lastly, the pre-service educators are aware of following safety protocols. As reported by Student MM, “We must observe the protocols rules and regulation that the high authorities are pointing out so that we do not get infected by the virus”. They also recognize the need “to develop new skills and challenge my capabilities”

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The mental health status of the pre-service educators is greatly challenged because of the current pandemic crisis.
2. Majority of the pre-service educators encounter problems related to personal, educational and family concerns.
3. Majority of the pre-service educators have developed self-care activities to maintain their physical and mental wellbeing.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. Care support system such as the family and school specifically the faculty and guidance counsellors extend assistance in the different aspects of life of the pre-service educators to help them become resilient and overcome the challenges brought about by the pandemic crisis.
2. Specific strategies be crafted to address the problems encountered by the pre-service educators in relation to the personal, educational, and family concerns of the students.
3. Modules on self-care activities be crafted and integrated in the CFE classes to uphold the students’ holistic wellbeing.

References

- Arenas, D. L., Viduani, A. C., Bassols, A. M. S., & Hauck, S. (2020). Peer support intervention as a tool to address college students’ mental health amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 0020764020954468.
- Bartlett, J. D., Griffin, J., & Thomson, D. (2020). Resources for supporting children’s emotional well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Child Trends*.

- Billings, D. W., Folkman, S., Acree, M., & Moskowitz, J. T. (2000). Coping and physical health during caregiving: The roles of positive and negative affect. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 79, 131–142.
- Cohen, R. I. S., & Bosk, E. A. (2020). Vulnerable youth and the COVID-19 pandemic. *Pediatrics*, 146(1).
#CopingWithCOVID: A webinar series on young people and mental health.
<https://www.un.org/youthenvoy/2020/04/copingwithcovid-a-webinar-series-on-young-people-and-mental-health/>
- Courtney, D., Watson, P., Battaglia, M., Mulsant, B. H., & Szatmari, P. (2020). COVID-19 impacts on child and youth anxiety and depression: Challenges and opportunities. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 65(10), 688-691.
- Dhawan, S. (2020). Online learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 5-22.
- de Miranda, D. M., da Silva Athanasio, B., de Sena Oliveira, A. C., & Silva, A. C. S. (2020). How is COVID-19 pandemic impacting mental health of children and adolescents? *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 101845.
- Dvorsky, M. R., Breaux, R., & Becker, S. P. (2020). Finding ordinary magic in extraordinary times: Child and adolescent resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic. *European child & adolescent psychiatry*, 1-3.
- Folkman, S., Lazarus, R. S. (1988). Coping as a mediator of emotion. *Journal of Personal and Social Psychology*, 54, 466-75.
- Guessoum, S. B., Lachal, J., Radjack, R., Carretier, E., Minassian, S., Benoit, L., & Moro, M. R. (2020). Adolescent psychiatric disorders during the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown. *Psychiatry research*, 113264.
- Iivari, N., Sharma, S., & Ventä-Olkkonen, L. (2020). Digital transformation of everyday life—How COVID-19 pandemic transformed the basic education of the young generation and why information management research should care? *International Journal of Information Management*, 102183.
- India Today (2020). *Effect of Covid-19 on campus: Major steps being taken by colleges to keep education going.*
[https://www.indiatoday.in/education today/featurephilia/story/effect-of-covid-19-on-campus-steps-taken-by-colleges-1668156-2020-04-17.](https://www.indiatoday.in/education%20today/featurephilia/story/effect-of-covid-19-on-campus-steps-taken-by-colleges-1668156-2020-04-17)
- Jaishy, J., & Pandey, A. (2020). Family dynamics during lockdown. In Pandey, A. (Ed). *Mental health impact of quarantine and isolation. Handbook of Mental Health Issues During COVID19*, 40.
- Liang, L., Ren, H., Cao, R., Hu, Y., Qin, Z., Li, C., & Mei, S. (2020). The effect of COVID-19 on youth mental health. *Psychiatric Quarterly*, 1-12.
- Liu, C. H., Zhang, E., Wong, G. T. F., & Hyun, S. (2020). Factors associated with depression, anxiety, and PTSD symptomatology during the COVID-19 pandemic: Clinical implications for US young adult mental health. *Psychiatry Research*, 113172.
- Kapasias, N., Paul, P., Roy, A., Saha, J., Zaveri, A., Mallick, R., ... & Chouhan, P. (2020). Impact of lockdown on learning status of undergraduate and postgraduate students during COVID-19 pandemic in West Bengal, India. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 116, 105194.
- Manzoor, A. (2020). *Online teaching and challenges of COVID-19 for inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education.* [https://dailytimes.com.pk/595888/online-teaching-and-challenges-of-covid-19-for-inclusion-of-pwds-in-higher-education/.](https://dailytimes.com.pk/595888/online-teaching-and-challenges-of-covid-19-for-inclusion-of-pwds-in-higher-education/)
- Naciri, A., Baba, M. A., Achbani, A., & Kharbach, A. (2020). Mobile learning in higher education: Unavoidable alternative during COVID-19. *Aquademia*, 4(1), ep20016.
- Nicola, M., Alsafi, Z., Sohrabi, C., Kerwan, A., Al-Jabir, A., Iosifidis, C., ... & Agha, R. (2020). The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19): A review. *International journal of surgery (London, England)*, 78, 185.
- Oosterhoff, B., Palmer, C. A., Wilson, J., & Shook, N. (2020). Adolescents' motivations to engage in social distancing during the COVID-19 pandemic: Associations with mental and social health. *Journal of Adolescent Health*.
- Pandey, A. (2020.) *Mental health impact of quarantine and isolation. Handbook of Mental Health Issues during COVID19*, 40.
- Pfefferbaum, B., & North, C. S. (2020). Mental health and the Covid-19 pandemic. *New England Journal of Medicine*.
- Prakash, J., & Gupta, P. (2020). Common Mental Health Problems during COVID -19 Pandemic. In Pandey, A. (Ed). *Mental health impact of quarantine and isolation. Handbook of Mental Health Issues during COVID19*, 40

- Rauschenberg, C., Schick, A., Goetzl, C., Roehr, S., Riedel-Heller, S. G., Koppe, G., ... & Reininghaus, U. (2020). Social isolation, mental health and use of digital interventions in youth during the COVID-19 pandemic: A nationally representative survey.
- Shanahan, L., Steinhoff, A., Bechtiger, L., Murray, A. L., Nivette, A., Hepp, U., ... & Eisner, M. (2020). Emotional distress in young adults during the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence of risk and resilience from a longitudinal cohort study. *Psychological medicine*, 1-10.
- Shepperd, J. A., Maroto, J. J., & Pbert, L. A. (1996). Dispositional optimism as a predictor of health changes among cardiac patients. *Journal of Research in Personality* 30, 517–534.
- Singh, N. (2020). Social Media and its Impact on Mental Health. In Pandey, A. (Ed). Mental health impact of quarantine and isolation. *Handbook of Mental Health Issues During COVID19*, 40.
- Singh, K., & Yadav, J. (2020). Impact of mental health on academic performance of students during COVID-19 lockdown. In Pandey, A. (Ed). Mental health impact of quarantine and isolation. *Handbook of Mental Health Issues During COVID19*, 40.
- Strielkowski, W. (2020). *COVID-19 pandemic and the digital revolution in academia and higher education*.
- Tee, M. L., Tee, C. A., Anlacan, J. P., Aligam, K. J. G., Reyes, P. W. C., Kuruchittham, V., & Ho, R. C. (2020). Psychological impact of COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines. *Journal of affective disorders*, 277, 379-391.
- Toquero, C. M. (2020). Challenges and opportunities for Higher Education amid the COVID-19 pandemic: The Philippine context. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4).
- Wade, M., Prime, H., & Browne, D. T. (2020). Why we need longitudinal mental health research with children and youth during (and after) the COVID-19 pandemic. *Psychiatry Research*.
- Xie, X., Xue, Q., Zhou, Y., Zhu, K., Liu, Q., Zhang, J., & Song, R. (2020). Mental health status among children in home confinement during the coronavirus disease 2019 outbreak in Hubei Province, China. *JAMA pediatrics*.
- Yadav, J., & Srivastava, A. (2020). Child and adolescent mental health during the pandemic lockdown. In Pandey, A. (Ed). Mental health impact of quarantine and isolation. *Handbook of Mental Health Issues During COVID19*, 40.
- Yeasmin, S., Banik, R., Hossain, S., Hossain, M. N., Mahumud, R., Salma, N., & Hossain, M. M. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health of children in Bangladesh: A cross-sectional study. *Children and youth services review*, 117, 105277.
- Zhai, Y., & Du, X. (2020). Addressing collegiate mental health amid COVID-19 pandemic. *Psychiatry Research*, 113003.
- Zhang, X. B., Gui, Y. H., Xu, X., Zhu, D. Q., Zhai, Y. H., Ge, X. L., & Xu, H. (2020). Response to children's physical and mental needs during the COVID-19 outbreak. *World Journal of Pediatrics*, 1.

C. Signatories

Fe Yolanda Gatan-del Rosario

Dean, School of Teacher Education and Humanities

Susan A. Galamay, PhD

Lead proponent

Reiner Dulawan

Collaborator

Marlon Saludaes

Collaborator

Don Darwin M Dacles, PhD

URC Director

John Octavius S. Palina, PhD

University President